

21ST BLOOM TAXONOMY AS AN ADVANCED VERSION OF BLOOM TAXONOMY AND ITS IMPORTANCE IN CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN EDUCATION

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Abstract: Critical thinking skills are crucial in today's modern education processes, where higher-order thinking, synthesizing, analyzing, and problem-solving, decision-making skills are the keys to success in the domain that learners implement them. The article investigates the difference between Bloom Taxonomy and advanced Bloom Taxonomy, and the importance of the 21st century Bloom Taxonomy that have implemented skills as an improvement of critical thinking skills.

Keywords: Bloom's taxonomy, 21st century Bloom Taxonomy, Critical thinking skills, Education, Importance

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi zamonaviy ta'lim jarayonlarida tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalari juda muhimdir. Bu yerda oliy tartibli fikrlash, sintezlash, tahlil qilish va muammoni hal qilish, qaror qabul qilish ko'nikmalari o'rganuvchilar amalga oshiradigan domenda muvaffaqiyatga erishishning kalitlari hisoblanadi. Maqolada Bloom Taksonomiya va ilg'or Bloom Taksonomiya o'rtasidagi farq, tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalarini yaxshilash sifatida ko'nikmalarni amalga oshirgan XXI asr Bloom Taksonomiyasining ahamiyati o'rganiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Bloomning taksonomiyasi, XXI asr : Bloom taksonomiyasi, Tanqidiy fikrlash ko'nikmalari, ta'lim, tanqidiy fikrlashning ahamiyati

Аннотация: Навыки критического мышления имеют решающее значение в современных образовательных процессах, где навыки мышления высшего порядка, синтеза, анализа и решения проблем, принятия решений являются ключом к успеху в той области, в которой учащиеся их применяют.

В статье исследуется разница между таксономией Блума и продвинутой таксономией Блума, а также важность таксономии Блума 21 века, которая реализовала навыки как улучшение навыков критического мышления.

Ключевые слова: таксономия Блума, таксономия Блума 21 века, Навыки критического мышления, Образование, Важность

Introduction:

The 21st-century Bloom's Taxonomy portrays an advanced version of the original Bloom's Taxonomy, designed to align with the needs of education in the modern era. This enhanced taxonomy incorporates additional dimensions essential for nurturing critical thinking skills, which play a vital role in various spheres of education. By integrating the 21st-century Bloom's Taxonomy into instructional practices, educators can allow students to develop and boost their critical thinking abilities, leading to improve problem-solving, analysis, and decision-making skills. Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives was created by Benjamin Bloom and a group of psychologists dealing with cognitive skills to streamline the process of making standardized annual examinations and aligning educational goals across academic organizations (Bloom, 1956). The ultimate goal was to decrease the amount of labor required to administer these exams while promoting higher forms of thinking (Krathwohl, 2002). In 1956, Dr. Benjamin Bloom, an educational psychologist, in collaboration with Max Englehart, Edward Furst, Walter Hill and David Krathwohl put devised a theory to upgrade the teaching learning process from the lower level of learning and memorization to the higher level of analysis, evaluation, creativity and problem-solving approach. Bloom's Taxonomy includes three sphere of academic learning: cognitive, affective and psychomotor. The cognitive sphere comprises mental skills to produce knowledge, the affective sphere adds gradual emotional development of attitude, whereas, the psychomotor sphere encompasses physical skills. Thus, it is abbreviated as KSA (knowledge [cognitive], skills [psychomotor] and attitude [affective]). Originally, the cognitive domain was

based on these six stages: knowledge, comprehension, application, analysis, synthesis and evaluation (Bloom, 1956).

During the mid-nineties, Lorin Anderson, who was Bloom's student, along with David Krathwohl revised the cognitive domain with a new approach and added three changes (see Figure 1.) They rearranged the categories, changed their names from noun to verb form and created a process and a level of knowledge matrix¹.

Figure 1. Bloom's taxonomy of cognitive skills

The 21st-century Bloom's Taxonomy provides educators with a framework to design learning experiences that enhance critical thinking. By incorporating activities that require analysis, evaluation, and synthesis, educators can challenge students to think deeply, question assumptions, and critically evaluate information². This approach encourages students to develop intellectual independence, creativity, and the ability to apply their knowledge in real-world contexts.

Moreover, fostering critical thinking skills through the 21st-century Bloom's Taxonomy prepares students for lifelong learning and success in the digital age. In an era of information overload, critical thinking equips students with the skills to evaluate sources, distinguish reliable information, and think critically about the information they encounter³. These skills are essential for students to become self-

¹ Anderson, Krathwohl & Blooms, 2001

² Krathwohl, 2002

³ National Education Association, 2016

directed learners who can adapt to new challenges, engage in continuous learning, and thrive in a rapidly changing world.

The 21st-century Bloom's Taxonomy builds upon the original Bloom's Taxonomy and aims to reflect the skills and competencies needed in the 21st-century learning environment. While the original Bloom's Taxonomy focused primarily on cognitive domains, the 21st-century version incorporates additional dimensions such as technological skills, creativity, critical thinking, collaboration, and communication. Here is a comparison between the two taxonomies:

Original Bloom's Taxonomy:

The original Bloom's Taxonomy, proposed by Benjamin Bloom in the 1950s, categorized cognitive skills into six hierarchical levels: Knowledge, Comprehension, Application, Analysis, Synthesis, and Evaluation. It primarily focused on intellectual abilities and knowledge acquisition⁴.

21st-century Bloom's Taxonomy:

The 21st-century Bloom's Taxonomy expands on the cognitive skills of the original taxonomy and incorporates additional dimensions relevant to the modern era. It includes the following levels: Remembering, Understanding, Applying, Analyzing, Evaluating, and Creating. Additionally, it emphasizes skills such as critical thinking, problem-solving, communication, collaboration, and digital literacy⁵.

The 21st-century Bloom's Taxonomy acknowledges the evolving demands of the 21st-century workforce and the need for students to develop a broader range of skills beyond traditional knowledge acquisition. It recognizes the importance of creativity, innovation, digital literacy, and collaboration, which are crucial in preparing students for success in the modern world.

Table 1. Practical tool to use of Bloom's taxonomy for successful teaching.

⁴ Anderson 2001

⁵ Krathwohl 2001

Levels	Taxonomy	Outcomes	Words (Action Verbs)	Questions
Level 1	Remembering	Students recall important information	Arrange, Define, Describe, List, Match, Name, Order, Recall, Reproduce	(What, Who, Which) What can you remember about the event?
Level 2	Understanding	Students demonstrate knowledge of the issues acquired while doing so	Classify, Discuss, Explain, Identify, Report, Summarize	(Are you able to write in your own words...? Can you make a quick overview...? What are your thoughts on this....?) Summarize the event in your own words
Level 3	Applying	Focused with pupils' ability to implement their skills and information to a variety of circumstances	Apply, Calculate, Demonstrate, Interpret, Show, Solve, Suggest	(Do you have any further examples of...? Is it possible that this happened in...? Can you adopt the approach to a personal experience...?) Suggest how the main lessons in this event could help other young people
Level 4	Analysing	Pupils' ability to make links between ideas and to analyze critically	Analyse, Appraise, Compare, Contrast, Distinguish, Explore, Infer, Investigate	(What could have happened if...? How did this compare to...? What other results do you perceive as being possible?) Why did the different

				characters in the event behave the way that they did?
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(continued)

Students can then use the taxonomy to improve their own higher-level thinking as a result of this self-analysis. Most comprehensive courses, especially those with critical thinking as an aim, would seem to benefit from such a method⁶

Table 1. (continued)

Levels	Taxonomy	Outcomes	Words (Action Verbs)	Questions
Level 5	Evaluating	Students can use their experience and wisdom to draw inferences, identify creative solutions to issues, and defend findings	Argue, Assess, Critique, Defend, Evaluate, Judge, Justify	(Is there a smarter method to...? Assess the worth of...? Are you able to defend your viewpoint on...? How efficient are...?) Evaluate the strength of the main character's decision to leave
Level 6	Creating	Students show what they've learned by making something new, whether it's physical or abstract	Compose, Construct, Create, Devise, Generate, Organise, Plan, Produce	(Do you think you can come up with a solution to...? How would you manage with... if you had unlimited resources? Can you think of unique and

⁶ Hogan 1997

				unexpected ways to use...?) Rewrite the ending of this event, to show a different outcome
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In conclusion: the 21st-century Bloom's Taxonomy serves as an advanced version of the original taxonomy, incorporating dimensions that are essential for education in the modernized world. Its emphasis on enhancing critical thinking skills is supported by research⁷. By implementing this taxonomy, educators can design learning experiences that challenge students to think critically, analyze information, and make informed decisions. Cultivating critical thinking skills is crucial for students to boost academically, succeed in their professional lives, and become lifelong learners.

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⁷ Halpern, 2003; Ennis, 2011; Facione, 2015

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